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Deliverable 5.1

Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DEC) Plan

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Executive Summary

ARCFISH will develop a pilot Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) supporting sustainable fisheries in the Arctic. The DTO will be based on the existing Blue Insight platform that seamlessly supports the market segments of the ocean observing value chain of the New Blue Economy, also known as the Sustainable Blue Economy (SBE). The SBE is a concept that promotes sustainable development and conservation of ocean resources for economic, social, and environmental benefits. In the Arctic, sustainable fisheries focusing on achieving long-term sustainability and resilience of ocean ecosystems and communities is the key to uphold good living conditions for its residents. The project will target two key regions for Arctic fisheries: (1) Western Greenland, centred around Disko Bay, and (2) region around Iceland, northwards to the Svalbard archipelago and the Barents Sea.

The Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan lays out a set of approaches with the goal of maximising the visibility and impact of ARCFISH and its inherent activities. It outlines specific approaches towards DEC activities as they relate respectively to promotion of the project, sharing results, and facilitating and encouraging uptake of results. It describes the Tools and Channels that will be used, Target Audiences, Key Messages, and defines some Key Performance Indicators against which progress, and impact can be measured. Beginning with the creation of a visual identity (logo) that is easily identifiable and distinguishes ARCFISH from other projects or services, this plan will support the development of an excellent reputation for ARCFISH towards the fishing community, DTO community, various stakeholders and end users, and the wider public.

DEC efforts will focus on producing quality and appealing information content and passing this on to the target audiences through online (e.g. website, social media, e-newsletters, data sharing platform, virtual meetings) and offline channels (e.g. in-person events, workshops, presentations, posters, infographics, brochures).

The plan will be implemented from the outset of the project and monitored and updated throughout its duration. The DEC Plan will evolve during the lifespan of the project, in accordance with this process.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
DITTO	UN Ocean Decade Programme – Digital Twins of the Ocean
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
EC	European Commission
EDITO	European Digital Twin of the Ocean
EFCA	European Fisheries Control Agency
EMODNet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EMSO	European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEM	Greenland Ecosystem Modelling Programme
HELCOM	Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission (Helsinki Commission)
HiAOOS	High Arctic Ocean Observing System, Horizon Europe Project
ICES	International Council for the Exploration of the Sea
IOC	Intergovernmental Ocean Commission
IP/R	Intellectual Property / Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NERSC	Nansen Center for Environment and Remote Sensing
NMDC	Norsk Marine Data Centre
ODIS	Ocean Data Information System
SBEP	Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
TA	Target audience
UN	United Nations
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
WoRMS	World Register of Marine Species
WP	Work package

1. Introduction

1.1. Objectives of the ARCFISH Project

ARCFISH has the overall objective to develop a pilot Digital Twin of the Ocean delivering new data products and services for improved decision-making in fisheries management to support sustainability and resilience of Arctic fisheries.

The specific objectives are as follows:

1. Co-develop use cases for sustainable fisheries in the Arctic based on stakeholder needs, and analysis of available data sources and data gaps.
2. Develop services for ingesting relevant data into the ARCFISH DTO: (1) oceanographic data, (2) met-ocean-ice forecasts and reanalysis from models, (3) biological data and ecosystem model products, (4) fishery-dependent and resource management data, and (5) auxiliary data (e.g. bathymetry).
3. Create a regional database of ocean climate, environmental, and fisheries data for Arctic Fisheries.
4. Implement the Arctic fisheries use cases in the ARCFISH DTO, with services and tools for integrating, analysing, and visualising observations and predictions from available data sources, and preparing data products for use in decision and policy making.
5. Prepare training material for the diverse ARCFISH DTO users and organise capacity building events in conjunction with the annual project meetings and Blue Economy Partnership seminars.
6. Engage with other DTO projects and initiatives (e.g., ILIAD, EDITO, Blue-Cloud2026, EOSC, DITTO) to align ARCFISH DTO development with the EU DTO.
7. Make the regional database and selected data products from the ARCFISH DTO available through open data infrastructures and promote ARCFISH results through the iAOS portal.
8. Facilitate cooperation on developing sustainable economic activities in Arctic fisheries between actors in government, academia, and industry.

The use case will focus on two key regions for Arctic fisheries: (1) Western Greenland, centred around Disko Bay, and (2) region around Iceland, northwards to the Svalbard archipelago and the Barents Sea.

The project is comprised of three work packages focused on the development of the DTO and three complementary work packages (Figure 1). WP1 underpins the development of the DTO in WP2-WP4, by establishing the stakeholder base and setting up a strategy for co-development and engagement. WP2 provides data services for ingesting heterogeneous data (from fisheries data to oceanographical and other data relating to case studies) to the ARCFISH DTO platform. WP3 Based on stakeholder needs from WP1 and data ingested in WP2, partners will develop new data products for sustainable fisheries. WP4 will see the development of DTO components to visualise the new data products in 3D and 4D and includes testing and validation with the support of stakeholders (WP1). WP5 works to maximize the project's impacts through dissemination, communication and activities to boost exploitation. WP6 ensures the smooth management of the project, effective implementation, timely delivery, and efficient use of resources.

Figure 1 - ARCFISH work packages

1.2. Objectives of the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan

ARCFISH has one work package dedicated to Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC). The main objective of this work package is to promote the project and results to a wide audience of stakeholders through active online presence and a series of thematic events and demonstrations.

Fundamental to the DEC work in ARCFISH is the DEC Plan contained in this document. The plan outlines all the DEC activities foreseen during the project detailing the DEC tools to be developed, laying out the key messages for Target Audiences (e.g., policy and decision makers; business sector, data service providers, researchers; local communities, and the general public), and establishing key performance indicators (KPIs) to monitor the reach and impact of DEC actions. This document constitutes the first version of the DEC Plan and will be reviewed periodically and updated when needed.

1.3. Organization of the Report

This document begins with an introduction to the concepts of Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication and explains the role each component has in maximizing the impact of the project and the uptake of its outputs. Next, it describes the Key Target Audiences who will be addressed and the Key Messages that will be directed towards them. Then, it describes the Tools and Channels used for each of the three DEC components. Later, it outlines the Key Performance Indicators that will be used to track the impact of the DEC activities over time. A critical part of this document covers Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Management of the exploitable results produced. An outline plan is provided in the first version of this document, which will be expanded upon later in the project. Finally, the document describes the rights and obligations of the project and its beneficiaries with respect to the commitment to the funding authorities.

2. Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Elements

The DEC plan addresses three main components:

Dissemination ensures that the results and new findings of the project reach communities that need and can use them.

Exploitation deals with uptake, finding an end user for the results and products of the project, ensuring that the project has a practical application that can be used immediately by the stakeholders who need those resources and products.

Communication deals with the flow of information about the project to a general or mixed audience, to inform society about the objectives, activities, and achievement of the project throughout its entire lifecycle, as well as with the flow of information within the project consortium.

The plan is implemented through addressing the following questions:

Who are the target audiences for the ARCFISH specific outputs?

Why is ARCFISH relevant to these audiences?

What key messages does ARCFISH want to pass to these audiences?

How can these messages be tailored to their target audiences?

Through this approach, we will identify the tools and channels that will be used to communicate the specific messages with the target audiences, to disseminate project results and to encourage their engagement.

Beneficiary institutions, participating companies and individuals involved in ARCFISH will act as promoters and interpreters of the project's results. From its very beginning the project will start sharing the aim, goals, the DTO framework information, preliminary results and any other project achievement. Carefully crafted messages delivered through suitable channels will publicise ARCFISH work. The purpose will be to generate demand for the data and products developed; encourage typical and non-typical data users to use and exploit the project's results. DEC activities also aim to draw the attention of national and regional governments and other public and private funding sources to the needs and benefits of the innovation actions, and to attract the interest of supporting institutions. The final aim will be to enhance the reputation and visibility of ARCFISH at local, national and international levels.

2.1. Target Audiences

The Target Audiences for ARCFISH were defined around the Quadruple Helix for Innovation Model (Figure 2), in which policy, scientific community, industry and society work in tandem. This model for cooperation is thought to maximize innovation while focusing on the interests of the citizen.

Figure 2 - The Quadruple Helix the Quadruple Helix Model adapted by Fraunhofer (2016), originally developed by Carayannis and Campbell (2009). Copyright © 2015 Fraunhofer.

With this in mind, and in consultation with all project partners during the proposal stage, the following key target audiences have been identified for the communication and dissemination during the project’s lifetime and following its end:

2.1.1. Fishing Industry

The fishing industry is the first target group for ARCFISH DEC. The industry includes high profile organisations such as Sustainable Fishery Greenland and Icelandic Ocean Cluster. The ARCFISH consortium has direct links in the fishing industry through the project industry partners Brim h.f. and Trackwell h.f. The main DEC goals towards industry will be to support stakeholder engagement in WP1 and to help provide opportunities for industry partners to benefit from the new management tools and services being developed. This category can also include other stakeholders from the Blue sector with interests in aquafood, environmental topics, and others.

2.1.2. The Scientific Community

Fundamental and applied research community, including oceanography institutes. Those who are interested in the standardised and optimised use of data included on the DTO. The subgroups part of this group can be divided into:

- I. Research community, providers of fisheries advice, experts in fisheries ecology and stock assessment, environmental ecologists, ichthyologists, planktologists and marine biologists
- II. National research managers and funders
- III. Students/Early career scientist. The latter group includes students or early career scientists in, for example, fisheries biology, marine ecology, biology, climate science, computer science, intelligent systems, machine learning, which was primarily targeted (incl. research Infrastructures e.g. EMSO).

2.1.3. Marine Ecosystem Managers and Resource Managers

Managers, technical personnel and environmental stewards who are responsible for the management of natural resources, natural heritage, and environmental protection on local, regional, European or international levels. This category also includes those who are responsible for operational decision making and application of methods, tools, and best practices. Examples of members of this target audience include environmental protection agencies, ministries (e.g. Environment, Fisheries, Natural Resources), and similar or related authorities. This category also includes coordinating bodies such as ICES, EFCA, FAO, national fisheries authorities.

2.1.4. Data service and DTO platform providers

This target group includes scientists and engineers from research and industry who collect and manage data from various different disciplines in natural science. They include bodies such as the European Open Science Cloud, Pangaea, Fishbase, WoRMS, Seabase, EMODnet (Biology), SeaDataNet, NMDC, eCUDO, ODIS, GEM, etc. It also includes those working towards a Digital Twin of the Ocean including the project partner Kongsberg Discovery as well as others such as EDITO, Iliad, DITTO, and more.

2.1.5. Relevant Clusters and Initiatives

This target group includes other clusters and initiatives who are working towards similar goals. The first of these is the Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership (SBEP) Cluster that brings together all projects funded under the first call from the SBEP. It can also include cooperation with other projects and initiatives funded through the European Commission, such as HEU project clusters with HiAOOS, POMP and other Arctic projects, or initiatives such as the European Polar Cluster and All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance.

2.1.6. Policy And Decision Makers

Policy and decision makers constitute European and national authorities, as well as more regional or local authorities. It relates to those public governmental agencies that formulate, adopt, implement, evaluate, or change fisheries, environmental and marine-related policies with those decisions occurring at any governmental level. This might include institutions exclusively dedicated to the ocean (IOC), institutions with broader mandates but also dealing with ocean affairs (UNEP, FAO) and intergovernmental organisations (EU, HELCOM). Apart from high level agencies, this target group also includes European Members States' governmental bodies, national funding agencies, supporting agencies, officials, legislators, etc.

2.1.7. General Public

The General Public is a mixed audience consisting of citizens from a variety of demographic contexts: nationalities, ages, cultural and ethnic backgrounds, professional fields, and educational levels. As a target audience, the general public constitutes a heterogeneous audience. Therefore, the interests of this audience are very varied and sometimes in conflict with each other. Content directed towards the General Public will be unbiased, non-controversial, and will not assume any previous scientific or technical knowledge. It will be designed to be appealing and engaging to a broad range of tastes and to provide easy to understand, and interesting information about the project and its outputs in a simple and straightforward format.

2.1.8. Media

Where possible, local media will be engaged and informed about the latest news and developments from ARCFISH. This will be on a case-by-case basis, as popular media responds to news that is relevant to them in a particular moment or context. Examples of popular media that will form this target group includes CORDIS, Horizon Magazine, ECO Magazine, and other popular online magazines and media agencies as appropriate.

The editorial coverage in the press, or on the web, has the capacity to reach very large audiences. Beyond these, the consortium partners will make use of regional, national, and European media contacts. The consortium will make use of the media mailing lists of the EC and will contact the Information Communications Unit of the EC, where appropriate.

The tools for engagement for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication are described in Sections 2.3, 2.4, and 2.5, respectively. A summary of the activities that will be carried out with each of the target audiences is described in Table 1.

Table 1 - DEC Strategies and Pathways for Key Target Audiences.

Target Audience	Why	How	Impacts
Fishing Industry e.g. Sustainable Fishery Greenland, Icelandic Ocean Cluster	Depends on knowledge about sustainability, distribution, health, etc. of fishing stocks and factors that influence them.	Demonstrations, Workshops, Webinars, Industrial fairs/events, B2B meetings, Direct contact	Uptake of the tools and services to more sustainably manage resources, better economic performance, greater return on investment.
Scientific Community, e.g. EGU, ICES	Expert knowledge on fishery stock status, fish ecology, climate variability, oceanography, etc.	Workshops, conferences, webinars, demonstrations, publications	Use DTOs to better understand confounding factors in fisheries and fish ecology to better understand distribution patterns, tipping points, etc. in the face of climate change.
Marine Ecosystem Managers and Resource Managers	Depends on knowledge about sustainability, distribution, health, etc. of fishing stocks and factors that influence them.	Demonstrations, Workshops, Webinars, Industrial fairs/events, B2B meetings, Direct contact	Uptake of the tools and services to more sustainably manage resources, better economic performance, greater return on investment.

Target Audience	Why	How	Impacts
Data Service and DTO platform developers. e.g. GEM, NMDC, eCUDO, Zenodo, EDITO, DITTO	Expert knowledge on the extent of data available in Europe and the major data gaps	Webinars, Conferences, Demonstrations, Publications	Uptake of the tools and service, potential to contribute new data to expand and enrich the products.
Clusters and initiatives e.g. SBEP clusters, HEU clusters, DTO platforms	Working towards shared goals and objectives	Webinars, Conferences, Demonstrations, Website/Social, Media	Combined efforts strengthen outputs and tools with additional knowledge and data, and reduce stakeholder saturation.
Policy Makers e.g. Euro MPs, national authorities	Need DTO tools for decision support.	Webinars, Conferences, Demonstrations, Policy briefs, Direct contact	Direct exploitation of DTO tools for decision support and policy prioritisation. Improved food security and economic stability
General Public	Interest in knowing how technology is providing a better understanding of the natural environment.	Webinars, Public Events, Demonstrations, Website/social media	Greater understanding of the Arctic ecosystem, the ocean in general and management of its resources
Media e.g. CORDIS, Horizon Magazine, ECO Magazine	Give greater reach and more credibility to the project and outputs.	Webinars, Conferences, Demonstrations, Website/social media, Press releases, Direct contact	Build awareness of ARCFISH and DTOs, as well as SBEP programme and Mission Ocean

2.2. Key Messages

The following key messages will be transmitted through various media and communication channels throughout the project. The aim of defining key messages is to ensure that the messaging created is consistent and clear and in agreement with the project’s goals, objectives and values. The key messages will be selected and adapted based on the specific communication needs, project timeline, relevant context and circumstances. When part of a local communication plan, they will be adapted taking into consideration the local context, including language, and the internal institutional specifics, if applicable.

The list below is a provisional and dynamic selection of current key messages from ARCFISH. The messages may be slightly amended or altered to a certain extent within the project without any fundamental change of the core meaning conveyed. New messages may also be added as the project matures and results become available.

Message 1: ARCFISH is working to co-develop with stakeholders a digital twin of the ocean (DTO) for Arctic fisheries, including a regional database of ocean climate, environmental, and fisheries data for Arctic Fisheries.

Message 2: The ARCFISH DTO comprises: (1) oceanographic data, (2) met-ocean-ice forecasts and reanalysis from models, (3) biological data and ecosystem model products, (4) fishery-dependent and resource management data, and (5) auxiliary data (e.g. bathymetry).

Message 3: ARCFISH carries out its research in the context of two use cases: (1) Western Greenland, centred around Disko Bay, and (2) region around Iceland, northwards to the Svalbard archipelago and the Barents Sea.

Message 4: ARCFISH supports governance (policy and decision making) through the ARCFISH DTO by providing tools for integrating, analysing, and visualising observations and predictions from available data sources, and preparing data products for use in decision and policy making.

Message 5: ARCFISH contributes to the sustainable management and protection of marine and coastal ecosystems and fisheries resources, to avoid significant adverse impacts (UN SDG 14 Life Below Water).

2.3. Communication Tools and Activities

Communication activities will involve the use of mass media to share relevant information, raise awareness of the growing importance of ocean observation for the purpose of marine preservation and promote the project and its findings to various audiences, including groups beyond the project's own community. The creation of a coherent image, messages adapted to the specific audiences and the translation of scientific results into layman terms by science communication and ocean literacy principles will enable the broadest possible outreach of the project.

Dedicated communication tools and activities for sharing ARCFISH information to the target audiences, have been established. A description of these communication tools and activities follows.

2.3.1. Branding

The first element in maximizing the visibility of ARCFISH is the development of a unique and distinctive visual identity, comprising a logo, look and style by which the project will come to be known. This visual identity was delivered in July 2024 (M4) of the project and consists of a logo (Figure 3), with versions for a variety of applications for different colour backgrounds and contexts, as well as lettering and a colour scheme.

Figure 3 - Various configurations of the ARCFISH logo for various applications.

2.3.2. Templates

The project's general templates have been designed based on the standards and rules set out within the project's branding. As well as establishing uniformity and consistency, they also convey the common project visual identity. All project communication and management templates are available under the project's Microsoft Teams account.

PowerPoint Template

The standard PowerPoint template is shown in Figure 4. The template is a partially animated, modern presentation with dynamic slides and smooth transitions that can be adapted to any project-related presentation scenario.

Figure 4 - Slides from the standard PowerPoint template developed for ARCFISH.

Deliverables Template

The standard Deliverable template was designed for use by the consortium. The template includes layouts and formatting that will be common to all deliverables, as well as standardized cover pages. The deliverable template includes recognition of the various funding authorities and the SBEP Programme.

2.3.3. Brochure/Pamphlet

A digital brochure will be created during the first months of the project. It will serve as a basis on which the rest of the communication material within the project will be created. The characteristics will be that it is:

- highly optimisable for various digital mediums including the web,
- easily customizable to serve each partner’s needs,
- easily sharable across various social media channels,
- multi-screen compatible.

Online communication tools will also be uploaded on the website (see Section 2.3.4), distributed via social media channels (see Section 2.3.5) and distributed over partner's networks.

2.3.4. Website

The public project website is due to be published in September 2024, at <https://arcfish.eu/>. The website was established using the following criteria:

1. Simple usability;
2. Responsive web design;
3. Clear and accessible structure;
4. Appealing, accurate and updated content.

The ARCFISH project website, together with social media, will be the main channel for online communication of the project. The ARCFISH website will be the go-to hub for information about project activities, news and achievements, collaborations, outputs and engagement opportunities. The website will be completely responsive, designed to function on multiple devices and on various operating systems. Specifically, the website will provide the following initial information, which will be updated throughout the project lifetime to reflect the status of the project at any given time:

About: Objectives and Impacts, Partners, Management Structure, End Users.

Case Studies: Iceland Case Study, Greenland Case Study.

Results: Deliverables, Data, Publications, and ARCFISH DTO platform.

Training: Training Materials (coming later).

News & Events: News, Events, Press Releases.

A more thorough look at the ARCFISH website will be provided in October 2024 in a short report to accompany Deliverable 5.2 – Public website.

To increase the audience visiting the ARCFISH project website, partners' and collaborators' websites will cross-post content, e.g. News from ARCFISH, and encourage their audiences to visit the ARCFISH project website. An example of how partners' and collaborators' websites (EurOcean) can be used to promote the project is shown in Figure 5. Partner and project websites will also encourage visits to the ARCFISH social media pages.

Figure 5 - EurOcean features news about ARCFISH on their institutional website, June 2024.

2.3.5. Social Media

Social media accounts have been created for ARCFISH on Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube (Figure 6). Links with other relevant projects and initiatives have been established and will continue to be updated throughout the lifetime of ARCFISH. Each of these platforms offers access to a different form of content as well as a different type of user. Twitter, for example, is a fast-paced platform that provides up to the minute information on trending topics. It is widely used by many of ARCFISH' target audiences (see below) and is also a source of information regularly used by journalists and the popular media, influencers and leaders; therefore, Twitter will be the main channel used for ARCFISH communication and dissemination.

X Account: @ArcfishEu
Official Hashtag: #ARCFISH

LinkedIn Account: ARCFISH

YouTube channel: ARCFISH.EU

Figure 6 - ARCFISH Social Media Networks

Priorities for social media:

1. Original content from ARCFISH: News and updates from the project and its activities.
2. Original content which does not emerge from ARCFISH: Relevant news and events, trending topics that relate to the interests of the ARCFISH audience.
3. Re-posted content: Posts from other accounts on themes and topics of relevance to the ARCFISH audience. These posts will be used to get the attention of other organisations and initiatives (by reposting their content) and to broaden the ARCFISH community.

Original and re-posted content will be tagged wherever possible with links to the consortium partners, to the funders, to the SBEP and to any other collaborating entity. Hashtags will also be broadly used, and a new hashtag has been created for the project, #ARCFISH. Other relevant hashtags include #BlueEconomyEU, #Fisheries, #Arctic, #DigitalTwin, #Iceland, #Greenland.

2.4. Dissemination Tools and Activities

Although communication channels can and will be used to disseminate the project results, there is a collection of tools specifically designed to support dissemination at the broadest possible scale. These results-oriented channels are described in this section.

2.4.1. Peer Reviewed Publications

Peer-reviewed publications in reputable and high impact journals will be one of the central channels for reaching the research and ocean science communities. Thereby the results of the project will benefit from the professional approval and will benefit from the long-term availability provided by the archiving systems of these journals. In line with the EC requirements, peer-reviewed publications will be open and accessible to anyone, i.e., published via gold (no embargo) or green (self-archived) open access.

Target journals for the results of ARCFISH include but are not limited to:

- Arctic Journal,
- Data Intelligence,
- Environmental Reviews,
- Frontiers in Earth Science,
- Frontiers in Marine Science,
- Marine Technology Society Journal,
- Methods in Ecology and Evolution,
- Nature Scientific Data,
- Nature,
- Polar Science,
- Science.

2.4.2. Scientific Conferences

Where possible, ARCFISH results will be presented at European scientific meetings and conferences, and the results published in the proceedings of those events. Potential meetings and conferences for this project are listed below.

- American Geophysical Union (AGU),
- Arctic Circle,
- Arctic Frontiers,
- Arctic Science Summit Week (ASSW),
- EuroGOOS International Conferences,
- European Geophysical Union (EGU),
- GEO events,
- International Council for Exploration of the Sea (ICES) Annual Science Conference,
- Ocean Science Meetings (OSM),
- Oceanology International,
- OCEANS conferences,
- UN Ocean conferences.

2.4.3. Selected Contact Lists and Websites:

Updates and press releases about important milestones in the project and marked achievements will be sent to a selection of distribution lists and dedicated websites. These include, Research*EU Results (CORDIS), Arctic Today, Oceanbuzz, Marine and Oceans, Sea Technology, and more.

2.4.4. Deliverables and Other Digital Resources

Project deliverables, training material, and other digital resources will be made available through the ARCFISH Zenodo community¹, to guarantee their long-term preservation. Common search engines such

¹ [ARCFISH Zenodo community](#)

as Google Scholar and Microsoft Research are harvesting metadata for assets hosted at Zenodo and provide high visibility. The consortium will make available information relating to methods and tools with test datasets, and open reports produced within the project through the ARCFISH Zenodo Community². WP6 Deliverable - Data Management Plan describes the procedures for data management in ARCFISH.

2.5. Exploitation Tools and Activities

Exploitation in ARCFISH is strongly linked to Stakeholder engagement as these stakeholders will use the ARCFISH results beyond the lifetime of the project.

2.5.1. Stakeholder Engagement

Stakeholder engagement is central to ARCFISH, with the development of ambitious solutions for fisheries management depending on the involvement of various stakeholder including fishers, seafood processors, researchers, authorities, regulatory bodies, policy-and decision-makers. To this end, ARCFISH has dedicated a full work package to stakeholder engagement: WP1 Multi-stakeholder co-creation of the Arctic DTO. This includes a Deliverable, D1.1 Stakeholder Engagement Plan³ that explain the procedure for engaging with various target groups and potential end users.

2.5.2. Training Workshops and Materials

ARCFISH will partner with the Horizon Europe funded project HiAOOS⁴ – High Arctic Observing System, a project also developing digital services based on the Blue Insight platform. HiAOOS has a fully elaborated calendar for training throughout its five-year duration, and there is scope for ARCFISH to benefit from and contribute to that training. ARCFISH training material will be openly available in Zenodo.

ARCFISH will provide demonstrations of the Blue Insight platform with key stakeholders during the lifetime of the project. For this purpose documentation, online tutorials and selected datasets will be supplied online via Zenodo and the project website.

2.6. Barriers to Optimal Exploitation

The consortium has identified a series of potential barriers that could hamper the exploitation of the project results. These are summarised below:

Digital platform technologies: ARCFISH partners will deliver innovative digital technologies. There is significant competition between companies developing new DTO technologies; therefore, it is critical for the ARCFISH to be interoperable with other emerging innovations.

Utilisation of resources in the Arctic: The natural resources, climate change and geopolitics are drivers for the growth in traffic and human activities in the Arctic. This leads to a need for more regulations, standards and agreements for safe operations, environmental protection, and management of resources.

² [ARCFISH Zenodo community](#)

³ <https://zenodo.org/records/13445054>

⁴ <https://hiaos.eu/>

However, this might influence sharing of knowledge, technology, and data between actors in different countries. ARCFISH will act as open as possible, but as closed as necessary. Technological developments will, whenever necessary, be protected by licences and IPR.

Geopolitics: A barrier in Arctic research is evolving because of the conflict between the “West” and Russia. This creates difficulties in the research collaboration in the Arctic. The conflict influences access to geographic areas, openness in research and the future focus areas of research. These conflicts are unlikely to affect ARCFISH.

3. DEC Management and Reporting

The continuous reporting of dissemination is a specific tool for monitoring partners’ dissemination activity during the whole project. The reporting is carried out by each partner using an excel sheet template that will be provided by WP5 leaders. The excel sheet will be hosted by the Coordinator (NERSC) on the project Teams file sharing area and will contain the required input for continuous reporting.

The continuous reporting of communication activities will enable monitoring and evaluation of the impact of the project and will provide guidance for modification or redefinition of the DEC plan, if needed.

Partners will be asked to report every 3 months communication and dissemination activities they have performed. To facilitate accurate monitoring and assessment of the dissemination and communication activities, and to understand the impact of the actions carried out, all partners must register the activities that they implement and save evidence of the activities conducted (e.g. agenda/programme, participant list, photos, recording), with all evidentiary materials complying strictly with GDPR requirements.

Monitoring and tracking of website and social media usage, reach and engagement will be managed through Google Analytics (website) and social media integral monitoring tools (e.g., Twitter Analytics, LinkedIn Analytics). The results of DEC monitoring will be included in the regular reporting cycle under WP5.

3.1. Key Performance Indicators and Impact

Performance of the dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities will be monitored over the entire lifetime of the project. Information and data to support performance evaluation will be gathered through the continuous reporting provided by the partners. This continuous reporting will enable monitoring and evaluation of the impact of the project and will provide guidance for modification or redefinition of the DEC plan, if needed.

Monitoring of dissemination impacts will be carried out using existing trackers e.g., number of reads, number of followers, number of citations, for peer-reviewed publications, as provided by the publishers and by other platforms such as Research Gate, ISI Web of Knowledge, Scopus, or similar. Information such as “number of participants” at conference sessions, workshops and other dissemination events, will also be collected whenever possible.

For activities in support of exploitation, efforts will be made to assess the impact of the activity by performing a pre- and post-analysis of the knowledge, attitudes and understanding of the participants.

Table 3 provides a summary of the performance indicators (KPIs) that will be used for ARCFISH communication and dissemination activities.

Table 2 - Key Performance Indicators for ARCFISH DEC Plan

Channel	Metric	Metric Type
Conferences	Number of events attended	Quantitative
	Number and nature of Sectors addressed	Quantitative and Qualitative
	Number of attendees	Quantitative
Peer-Reviewed publications	Number of reads	Quantitative
	Number of citations	Quantitative
	Number of downloads	Quantitative
Social Media posts	Number of reads/view/likes	Quantitative
	Number of reposts	Quantitative
	Number of followers	Quantitative
Website	Number of visits	Quantitative
	Number of pages viewed	Quantitative
	Time spent per visit	Quantitative
	Bounce Rate	Quantitative
	User demographics	Quantitative
Communication Products	Number of products developed per audience	Quantitative
	Number of subscribers (newsletters)	Quantitative
Training events and workshops	Number of attendees	Quantitative
	Number and nature of Sectors addressed	Quantitative and Qualitative
Educational Materials	Number of products developed	Quantitative
	Number of online “hits” for educational pages and videos.	Quantitative

4. Intellectual Property Rights and Management

Intellectual property management is an essential element to Exploitation. Once results become useful assets to others, their value cannot be lost to their creator(s) and so, it is important to identify early on who is the owner of the various project results and outputs as well as consider how the results can be as open as possible to be of value to the broader community but as closed as necessary to protect the author(s) or originator(s) of the knowledge.

The Horizon Europe, the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, has established a set of rules concerning the exploitation and dissemination of project results, including their protection through intellectual property (IP), with the aim to better protect and reap commercial and economic benefits from EU-funded research and innovation initiatives. This Sustainable Blue Economy project will follow these norms.

The ARCFISH Consortium will ensure that IPR is properly handled and will activate protection measures when needed. This is organised in WP6 in the context of the Data Management Plan, led by the Coordination Team. Further, in ARCFISH, a comprehensive plan for the uptake of ARCFISH results will be addressed through a dedicated Exploitation task, Task 5.3 Exploitation Synthesis, and the development of D5.5 Exploitation Synthesis, due in M26 (May 2026).

All knowledge and IPR management measures have been defined by the ARCFISH Consortium in pursuance of provisions contained in the national Grant Agreements (GAs) and in the Consortium Agreement (CA), which are the main references in terms of legal framework

4.1. Rights and Obligations for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

4.1.1. Logos, Acknowledgements and Hashtags

ARCFISH adheres to the guidelines provided by the SBEP Secretariat with respect to the use of logos and the acknowledgement of financial support as outlined in the document, “Website and Social Media Guidelines.” These include the use, in both online and offline communications, of the following logos:

4. Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership,
5. Funding partners corresponding to ARCFISH,
6. Co-funded by the European Union,
7. European Commission.

Further, on social media, ARCFISH follows the practice of tagging funding authorities, as well as the use of the SBEP official hashtag, **#BlueEconomyEU**.

ARCFISH has also added the following disclaimer to its products, where possible and practical, “Co-funded by the European Union through the Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership, The Research Council of Norway (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark, The National Centre for Research and Development, Poland (NCBR); The Icelandic Centre for Research, Iceland (RANNIS); and Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT). Views and opinions expressed, however, are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the national research agencies. Neither the European Union nor the granting authorities can be held responsible for them.”

4.1.2. Obligation to Keep Track of Results

Partners must keep track of all their dissemination and communication activities, all of which should be reported by each partner at the designated reporting stages. Partners are required to report on a quarterly basis any publication and dissemination activities using the template provided by EurOcean and NERSC. These reports contain information on activities carried out during the past quarter as well as activities foreseen in the coming quarter. Partners are encouraged to take photos of communication and dissemination activities in which they take part, always complying strictly with GDPR requirements.

Abstracts, posters, presentations, links, and other relevant material related to these activities should be provided by the project partner, along with the quarterly report.

5. Conclusions

ARCFISH has outlined a comprehensive DEC plan, providing guidelines for communication and dissemination to different audiences and through different channels. These guidelines are designed to support all other work packages in the project by providing a set of visually appealing tools with consistent look and feel that can help build confidence in ARCFISH and its messaging. The DEC plan is particularly relevant to WP1, where extensive contact with stakeholders takes place.

This document may be updated and improved throughout the lifetime of the ARCFISH project.

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